

INFLUENCE OF PREHEATING CONDITIONS ON THE DEGRADATION OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCED POLYPROPYLENE

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Keywords: Mechanical properties, Maleic anhydride grafted polypropylene, Thermal oxidative degradation

ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTP) show very good mechanical properties and weight saving benefits. And CFRTP has the characteristics of recycling efficiency, enables high-cycle molding and so on. On the other hands, it is thought that mechanical properties of CFRTP are affected by molding conditions, because of a thermal oxidative degradation by heat exposure. In this study, the polymer degradation behavior during preheating process was studied in order to improve the molding process of CFRTP. Specifically, the thermal gravimetric behavior of maleic acid modified polypropylenes (MAPP) was determined in dry air in order to be used to provide basis of thermal oxidative degradation of polypropylene. And the influence of exposure time to change mechanical properties of MAPP was investigated. The relationships between exposure condition and the change of flexural modulus of PP was clarified by using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC).

1 INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, energy conservation has become a hot topic world-widely. More and more scientists are focusing on how to improve the efficiency of current energy consumption mechanism. Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) show very good mechanical properties and weight saving benefits [1, 2]. According to excellent mechanical properties, carbon fiber reinforced thermosetting (CFRTS) have been already applied to various fields such as aircraft and sporting goods. However, because of low productivity and formability, it has not been widely applied to mass-produced products, such as mass-production automobile. In order to solve these problems, carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic (CFRTP) has been developed. Because it is excellent in the balance of formability and mechanical properties [3, 4]. Additionally, CFRTP has the characteristics of recyclability and high-cycle moldability, compared with CFRTS.

Nevertheless, CFRTP is exposed to the most severe thermal environment during high cycle molding process including the rapidly heating process. Hence mechanical properties of CFRTP are concerned to be affected by the molding process, because of the thermal oxidative degradation by heat exposure.

In detail, in order to achieve high-cycle molding for mass production, stamping forming is optimal. In this process, intermediate substrate of CFRTP is heated in a preheating process such as infrared (IR) heater to reach the upper to melting point of CFRTP. And then the melted substrate are formed by a mold of lower than melting temperature [5]. In this step, the cycle time can be shortened by the mold without heating and cooling cycle. Therefore reduction of manufacturing cost is expected. However, if the preheating process is oxidized at high temperature atmosphere, the degradation of the matrix resin will occur [6] and the mechanical properties will be further decreased [7-9]. The aim of this study is to understand the influence of preheating process on the mechanical properties of matrix resin.

In this paper, the resin degradation behavior in preheating process was investigated by three steps. Firstly, the thermal gravimetric behavior of maleic acid modified polypropylenes (MAPP) was determined in dry air and used to provide basis of thermal oxidative degradation of polypropylene. Secondly, we considered exposure time influence to extend of thermal oxidative degradation, which

we called as heat aging process. At last, the relationships between exposure condition and the change of flexural modulus of PP was clarified by using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC).

2 EXPERIMENT

2.1 Materials

Homo PP (Y6005GM, MFR=60g/10min at 230 degrees Celsius/2.16 kg) was produced by Prime Polymer Co. (Tokyo, Japan). Maleic anhydride grafted polypropylene (MA-g-PP, Yumex 1010) was produced by Sanyo Chemical Industries. The maleic-acid content in the MA-g-PP was 10%.

Other different percentage of maleic acid modified polypropylenes (MAPP) as shown in Table 1 were prepared by kneaded Homo PP and MA-g-PP. The specimens were kneaded by an extruder (Labo Plastomill 10C100S90, Toyo Seiki, Japan) for 15 minutes at 185 degrees Celsius by 30 rpm.

Table 1: Different type of polypropylene used in this study.

Sample Name	Homo PP	MA-0.5	MA-1.0	MA-g-PP
Homo PP (wt. %)	100	95	90	0
Yumex 1010 (wt. %)	0	5	10	100

2.2 Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

In order to discuss the thermal stability, the weight reduction by thermal degradation was measured by using a thermogravimetric analyzer (TA instruments, Discovery TGA). The measuring temperature range was from 30 to 600 degrees Celsius, with a heating rate of 10 degrees Celsius per minute. The measurement was conducted in two types of gas, dry air and nitrogen atmosphere, with a flow rate of 20 ml/min.

2.3 Heat aging process

The specimens were heated from room temperature to 200 degrees Celsius in order to conduct the thermal oxidative aging by IR heater (NGK INSULATORS, LTD.). In this process, the heating time until 200 degrees Celsius was changed by preset temperature of equipment. Three levels of preheating time condition as long, middle and short, were obtained. No heat aging specimens called as virgin in this study. The image of heat aging process and the image of cooling process are shown in Figures 1 and 2.

Figure 1: Image of heat ageing process.

Figure 2: Image of cooling process.

2.4 Preparation of specimens

Specimens were prepared by compression molded with a compression machine (Mini TEST PRESS-10, Toyo Seiki, Japan). The polypropylene pellets were heated up to 195 degrees Celsius for 10 minutes without pressure. After melting process, compressive press was carried out and holding for 3 min with 12 MPa by hydraulic cylinder. And then the specimen was cooled down to the room temperature by water with maintaining the pressure. The specimens were cut for mechanical property tests by diamond cutter.

2.5 Three point bending tests

The mechanical properties of PP were measured by three point bending test according to ISO 178 with universal testing machine (Shimadzu Co., AGS-X). The specimen had a span to thickness ratio of 16:1. The crosshead speed was 2 mm/min.

2.6 Izod impact tests

Unnotched Izod impact energy absorption was measured according to ISO 180 on an impact tester (Instron Co., POE2000e) at 25 degrees Celsius. The size of specimens is the width of 10 mm, the length of 40 mm and the thickness of 1.85 mm.

2.7 Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

Crystallinity of polypropylene after heat aging was measured by using differential scanning calorimetry (NETZSCHE, DC200F3 Maia) with nitrogen atmosphere. Measurement temperature range was from 30 to 210 degrees Celsius with a heating rate of 10 degrees Celsius per minute.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Thermogravimetric analysis

Thermal degradation of polymer are known to be significantly affected by oxygen. Reaction is divided into two types, one is pyrolysis without existence of oxygen, and another is thermal oxidative degradation with existence of oxygen. It is known that thermal oxidative degradation occurs easily at low temperature compared to pyrolysis [10].

The effect of oxygen on the thermal degradation was examined by measuring the thermal weight loss of the four types of PP specimens. The weight reduction curve of MAPP, MA-g-PP and Homo-PP were measured in two kinds of atmosphere, nitrogen (Figure 3 a) and dry air (Figure 3 b). The degradation temperature of MA-g-PP was the lowest among the four types of specimens in both atmospheres. In nitrogen atmosphere, transition of degradation temperature of MAPP was not observable due to maleic acid contents. On the contrary, in dry air atmosphere, degradation temperature of MAPP increased with increasing maleic acid content. However, the start point of weight reduction temperature decreased with increasing the maleic acid content in air atmosphere.

In comparison of the results in both atmospheres, these results showed that the dry air atmosphere containing oxygen, a kind of active gases, was easier to induce thermal decomposition than nitrogen. It is widely known, in the case of nitrogen atmosphere without oxygen, thermal oxidative degradation was hindered [11]. Therefore, degradation temperature of MAPP and Homo PP decreased to 150 degrees Celsius in dry air atmosphere than in nitrogen atmosphere. From the above, the thermal degradation temperature is varied by the purge gas. It is also shown that the thermal stability becomes lower in excess maleic acid-modified PP both with and without oxygen.

Figure 3: Weight reduction curves in nitrogen (a) and dry air (b) atmosphere of various polypropylenes.

3.2 Mechanical property

3.2.1 Three point bending tests

The mechanical properties of Homo PP and MAPP after heated were measured by three point bending tests in order to discuss the effect of preheating condition on mechanical properties of polypropylene. Flexural modulus, failure strain and flexural strength were shown in Figures 4-6.

At first, Figure 4 shows that the flexural modulus of heated modified PP were higher than virgin one in each case of maleic acid content. The flexural modulus of the middle aged specimens was the highest in all types of polypropylene. For crystalline polymer, it is said that the higher crystallinity ordinarily makes modulus higher. Therefore, it is presumed that crystallinity of each type of PP was increased by heat exposure.

On the other hand, failure strain has rapidly reduced even after the short heat aging despite amount of maleic-acid. According to mechanisms of thermal oxidative degradation [11, 12], heat ageing probably makes polymer chains to short. The short molecular chain led to more chain ends in the structure. Thus cracks were likely to occur in such structure. This results showed that both Homo PP and MAPP become brittle by heating regardless of heat aging time. Hence failure strain was reduced.

Next, flexural strength indicated lower values than virgin after heat aging. This result probably was caused by rapidly reduction of failure strain.

Figure 4: Influence of the heat exposure on the flexural modulus of polypropylenes.

Figure 5: Influence of the heat exposure on the failure strain of polypropylenes.

Figure 6: Influence of the heat exposure on the flexural strength of polypropylenes.

3.2.2 Izod impact tests

Figure 7 shows that impact energy absorption was decreased after heat aging regardless of the addition of maleic acid. It was considered that impact energy absorption affected by the three-point bending failure strain. Because materials were embrittled by heating as shown in Figure 5. It is considered that the energy absorption capability was decreased. It should be paid attention that heating condition probably decrease dynamic mechanical properties.

Figure 7: Influence of the heat exposure on the impact energy absorption of polypropylenes.

3.3 Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

The melting endothermic energy amount was measured in order to estimate crystallinity of polypropylene after heat ageing by DSC. The results were shown in Figures 8-11. The amount of melting endothermic of middle ageing sample was the largest in all types of polypropylene. Although the cooling condition of each samples were same (Figure 2). It is said that the crystallinity is affected by cooling condition. Nevertheless, from this result, Figure 11 shows that the variation of heat aging condition lead to the degree change of crystallinity. Thus the flexural modulus was changed by the heating condition. This phenomenon also revealed in each type of PP.

Figure 8: Calorie absorption rate of Homo PP measured by DSC with various aging time.

Figure 9: Calorie absorption rate of MA-0.5 measured by DSC with various aging time.

Figure 10: Calorie absorption rate of MA-1.0 measured by DSC with various aging time.

Figure 11: Heat of fusion of polypropylene

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, thermal stability of Homo PP, MAPP, MA-g-PP are investigated first. The influence of heat aging on mechanical properties of Homo PP and MAPP are also investigated. Then, results of DSC provide the reason to the change in flexural modulus.

From TGA

- (1) The thermal stability becomes lower in excess maleic acid modified PP in both atmospheres. It is easy to lead thermal degradation in the presence of oxygen.

From mechanical properties

- (2) The flexural modulus becomes higher, but the failure strain is decreased after heat aging. In other words, the polymer becomes brittle by heat exposure.
- (3) Regardless of both additional amount of maleic acid and heating time, it was found that failure strain decreased in quite a short heat exposure time.

From DSC

- (4) It is found that the variation of heat aging condition led to the degree change of crystallinity. Therefore the flexural modulus changed by heating time. However, the change degree was found varying with the amount of maleic acid and with the heating time.

The relationship between heat ageing time and changes of the melting endothermic are currently under investigation. Additionally, changes of the melting endothermic due to degree of maleic acid are also under investigation.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Part of this study belongs to Japanese METI project "the Future Pioneering Projects / Innovative Structural Materials Project" since 2013fy. Authors would like to express sincerely appreciation to the project members who have provided valuable materials and useful information.

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